

NEWTON'S METHOD IN MIXED-PRECISION

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Abstract. We investigate the use of reduced precision arithmetic to solve the linear equation for the Newton step. If one neglects the backward error in the linear solve, then well-known convergence theory implies that using single precision in the linear solve has very little negative effect on the nonlinear convergence rate.

However, if one considers the effects of backward error, then the usual textbook estimates are very pessimistic and even the state-of-the-art estimates using probabilistic rounding analysis do not fully conform to experiments. We report on experiments with a specific example. We store and factor Jacobians in double, single, and half precision. In the single precision case we observe that the convergence rates for the nonlinear iteration do not degrade as the dimension increases and that the nonlinear iteration statistics are essentially identical to the double precision computation. In half precision we see that the nonlinear convergence rates, while poor, do not degrade as the dimension increases.

Audience. This paper is intended for students who have completed or are taking an entry-level graduate course in numerical analysis and for faculty who teach numerical analysis. The important ideas in the paper are O notation, floating point precision, backward error in linear solvers, and Newton's method.

Key words. Newton's Method, Mixed-Precision Arithmetic, Backward Error, Probabilistic Rounding Analysis

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1. Introduction. The entry level numerical analysis curriculum at the graduate level typically includes

- a description of IEEE floating point arithmetic,
- direct methods for linear equations, especially Gaussian elimination and the LU factorization,
 - estimates of backward error in terms of the size of the problem, and
- Newton's method for nonlinear equations.

However these courses do not usually connect these topics. The purpose of this paper is to do that and to apply recent results on probabilistic rounding analysis [12–14,17] to the convergence analysis of the nonlinear Newton iteration. In particular, we will show how the precision used for the linear solve for the Newton step can be less than that for computing the nonlinear residual with no loss in the speed of convergence or the quality of the solution of the nonlinear iteration.

In § 2 we review how the classic [19] convergence estimate for Newton's method is affected by the error in the Jacobian. In § 2.2 we connect that estimate with the backward error in the linear solver. We then review the standard estimates [7,10] for this error and explain how the new results in [13,14,17] affect the nonlinear convergence analysis.

Finally in § 3 we illustrate the results with a numerical example using double, single, and half precision [16,30] for the linear solve. These results and the theory in § 2 indicate that one can safely do the linear solve in single precision if the Jacobian itself is computed to single precision accuracy. This example is large enough to see the effects of increasing the dimension of the problem, at least in half precision, but small enough that the reader can do the computation on a desktop machine.

The theory breaks down if the Jacobian is singular at the solution and we also present an example of that case to illustrate the effects of singularities.

1.1. Notation. In this paper we denote vectors by boldfaced lower case letters and matrices by boldfaced upper case letters, for example \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{A} . We denote the i th component of \mathbf{x} by x_i to distinguish it from the i th member of a sequence of vectors \mathbf{x}_i . We denote the ij th entry of \mathbf{A} by \mathbf{A}_{ij} .

2. Local Error Estimates for Newton's Method. Most of the material in this section is standard and one can find more details in [8,19–21,29]. The novelty will come in § 2.2, where we explore the connection between the nonlinear convergence estimate, the backward error in the nonlinear solver, and new probabilistic rounding results from [13,14].

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45 We consider nonlinear systems of equations

46 (2.1)
$$\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}) = 0.$$

47 In (2.1) $\mathbf{F} : D \rightarrow R^N$ where D is an open convex subset of R^N . We will let \mathbf{F}' denote the Jacobian matrix

48
$$\mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x})_{ij} = \partial f_i(\mathbf{x}) / \partial x_j$$

49 where

50
$$\mathbf{F} = (f_1, f_2, \dots, f_N)^T.$$

51 We will impose a norm $\|\cdot\|$ on R^N and let $\|\cdot\|$ also denote the induced matrix norm.

52 The Newton iteration for solving (2.1) takes a current approximation \mathbf{x}_c of a solution to a new approxi-
53 mation \mathbf{x}_+ via

54 (2.2)
$$\mathbf{x}_+ = \mathbf{x}_c - \mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x}_c)^{-1} \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}_c).$$

55 The Newton iteration is defined if \mathbf{F} is differentiable at \mathbf{x}_c and $\mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x}_c)$ is nonsingular. In this paper we assume
56 that we compute the Newton step

57
$$\mathbf{s} = -\mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x}_c)^{-1} \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}_c)$$

58 by solving the linear equation

59 (2.3)
$$\mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x}_c) \mathbf{s} = -\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}_c)$$

60 with Gaussian elimination with column pivoting [7, 11].

61 We make the standard assumptions [8, 19, 29] for local convergence:

62 ASSUMPTION 2.1. *There is $\mathbf{x}^* \in D$ such that*

- 63 • $\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}^*) = 0,$
- 64 • $\mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x}^*)$ is nonsingular, and
- 65 • $\mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x})$ is Lipschitz continuous with Lipschitz constant γ , i. e.

66 (2.4)
$$\|\mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x}) - \mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{y})\| \leq \gamma \|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}\|,$$

67 for all $\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y} \in D$.

68 Assumption 2.1 implies that the Newton iteration (2.2) is defined for all \mathbf{x}_c sufficiently near \mathbf{x}^* .

69 The convergence estimates in this section neglect any error in the linear solver and assume that the
70 solution of (2.3) is exact. We will use the standard notation for errors

71
$$\mathbf{e} = \mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}^* \text{ for } \mathbf{x} \in D.$$

72 For example, if \mathbf{x}_c is the current point in the iteration, then $\mathbf{e}_c = \mathbf{x}_c - \mathbf{x}^*$ is the current error.

73 We will begin by quoting the classic local convergence theorem. We will also give the proof because it
74 is illuminating and uses a familiar result from an entry level numerical linear algebra course.

75 LEMMA 2.1. *Suppose \mathbf{A} is nonsingular and*

76 (2.5)
$$\|\mathbf{A} - \mathbf{B}\| \leq \frac{1}{2\|\mathbf{A}^{-1}\|}$$

77 then \mathbf{B} is nonsingular, $\|\mathbf{B}^{-1}\| < 2\|\mathbf{A}^{-1}\|$, and

78 (2.6)
$$\|\mathbf{A}^{-1} - \mathbf{B}^{-1}\| \leq 2\|\mathbf{A}^{-1}\|^2 \|\mathbf{A} - \mathbf{B}\|.$$

79 THEOREM 2.2. *Assume that Assumption 2.1 holds, then*

80 (2.7)
$$\|\mathbf{e}_c\| \leq \frac{1}{2\|\mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x}^*)^{-1}\|\gamma},$$

81 and that the ball

$$82 \quad (2.8) \quad \{\mathbf{x} \mid \|\mathbf{e}\| \leq \|\mathbf{e}_c\|\} \subset D.$$

83 Then

$$84 \quad (2.9) \quad \|\mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x}^*)^{-1}\|/2 \leq \|\mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x}_c)^{-1}\| \leq 2\|\mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x}^*)^{-1}\|.$$

85 Moreover, if \mathbf{e}_+ is the Newton iterate from \mathbf{x}_c (2.2), then

$$86 \quad (2.10) \quad \|\mathbf{e}_+\| \leq \gamma\|\mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x}^*)^{-1}\|\|\mathbf{e}_c\|^2 \leq \|\mathbf{e}_c\|/2.$$

87 *Proof.* We can use Lipschitz continuity (2.4) and (2.7) to invoke Lemma 2.1 because

$$88 \quad \|\mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x}_c) - \mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x}^*)\| \leq \gamma\|\mathbf{e}_c\| \leq \frac{1}{2\|\mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x}^*)^{-1}\|}.$$

89 Hence $\mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x}_c)$ is nonsingular and

$$90 \quad (2.11) \quad \|\mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x}_c)^{-1}\| \leq 2\|\mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x}^*)^{-1}\|.$$

91 Since $\mathbf{x}^* + t\mathbf{e}_c \in D$ for all $0 \leq t \leq 1$ by assumption (2.8), the fundamental theorem of calculus implies
92 that

$$93 \quad (2.12) \quad \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}_c) = \int_0^1 \mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x}^* + t\mathbf{e}_c)\mathbf{e}_c dt.$$

94 Subtract \mathbf{x}^* from both sides of (2.2) and use (2.12) to obtain

$$\begin{aligned} 95 \quad \mathbf{e}_+ &= \mathbf{e}_c - \mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x}_c)^{-1}\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}_c) = \mathbf{e}_c - \mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x}_c)^{-1} \int_0^1 \mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x}^* + t\mathbf{e}_c)\mathbf{e}_c dt \\ &= \mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x}_c)^{-1} \left(\int_0^1 (\mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x}_c) - \mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x}^* + t\mathbf{e}_c)) dt \mathbf{e}_c \right). \end{aligned}$$

96 Hence, using (2.11) and Lipschitz continuity again

$$\begin{aligned} 97 \quad \|\mathbf{e}_+\| &\leq \|\mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x}_c)^{-1}\| \gamma \int_0^1 (1-t) dt \|\mathbf{e}_c\|^2 \\ &= \|\mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x}_c)^{-1}\| \gamma/2 \|\mathbf{e}_c\|^2 \leq \gamma\|\mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x}^*)^{-1}\|\|\mathbf{e}_c\|^2, \end{aligned}$$

98 which completes the proof using (2.7). □

99 In many courses (2.10) is expressed with O -notation

$$100 \quad \|\mathbf{e}_+\| = O(\|\mathbf{e}_c\|^2).$$

101 This is appropriate when the asymptotic convergence rate is more important in the discussion than the
102 *prefactor* $\gamma\|\mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x}^*)^{-1}\|$. That will be the case in this paper and we will use O -notation throughout. Moreover,
103 the precise condition (2.7) can be replaced by “ \mathbf{x}_0 is sufficiently close to \mathbf{x}^* ” for the discussion in this paper.
104 Having said that, the presence of $\|\mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x}^*)^{-1}\|$ is a clear and correct indicator that Theorem 2.2 does not hold
105 if $\mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x}^*)$ is singular. We will warn the reader a few more times about the presence of $\|\mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x}^*)^{-1}\|$ in the
106 O -terms.

107 All one needs to describe the entire Newton iteration is an estimate like (2.10) that describes the evolution
108 of the error from one iteration the next. Repeated applications of Theorem 2.2 imply Corollary 2.3.

109 **COROLLARY 2.3.** *Assume that Assumption 2.1 holds. Then if \mathbf{x}_0 is sufficiently near \mathbf{x}^* , the Newton
110 iteration exists (i. e. $\mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x}_n)$ is nonsingular for all n) and converges to \mathbf{x}^* . Moreover the convergence is
111 q -quadratic*

$$112 \quad \|\mathbf{e}_{n+1}\| = O(\|\mathbf{e}_n\|^2)$$

113 In § 3 we plot on a semi-log scale the histories of relative residuals $\|\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}_n)\|/\|\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}_0)\|$ as a function of
 114 n . In the q-quadratic case the curve is concave, as we see in the figures. The relative residual is a good
 115 surrogate for the relative error if $\mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x}^*)$ is well-conditioned. In fact, if Assumption 2.1 and (2.7) hold, then
 116 (see [19] page 72)

$$117 \quad (2.13) \quad \frac{\|\mathbf{e}_n\|}{4\kappa(\mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x}^*))\|\mathbf{e}_0\|} \leq \frac{\|\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}_n)\|}{\|\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}_0)\|} \leq \frac{4\kappa(\mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x}^*))\|\mathbf{e}_n\|}{\|\mathbf{e}_0\|}.$$

118 In (2.13)

$$119 \quad \kappa(\mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x}^*)) = \|\mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x}^*)\| \|\mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x}^*)^{-1}\|$$

120 is the condition number of $\mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x}^*)$.

121 **2.1. Errors in the Function and Jacobian.** Theorem 2.2 gives an idealized description of what one
 122 can expect in computations. Even so, the predictions are very accurate for all but the final step or two of
 123 a nonlinear iteration. Theorem 2.4 makes this precise. The objective of this paper is to explore the effects
 124 of errors in the Jacobian and in the linear solver on the idealized analysis in Theorem 2.2. To that end, we
 125 consider an iteration

$$126 \quad (2.14) \quad \mathbf{x}_+ = \mathbf{x}_c - \mathbf{J}(\mathbf{x}_c)^{-1}(\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}_c) + \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{x}_c)).$$

127 In (2.14) $\mathbf{J}(\mathbf{x}_c)$ is an approximation of $\mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x}_c)$. One example is a finite-difference approximation of the
 128 Jacobian. The term $\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{x}_c)$ is the error in $\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}_c)$.

129 We will assume that the errors in the function and Jacobian are uniformly bounded

$$130 \quad (2.15) \quad \|\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{x})\| \leq \epsilon_F \text{ and } \|\mathbf{J}(\mathbf{x}) - \mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x})\| \leq \epsilon_J \leq \frac{1}{4\|\mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x}^*)^{-1}\|}$$

131 for all \mathbf{x} sufficiently near \mathbf{x}^* . The reader may think of ϵ_F as double precision floating point error, even
 132 though that is generally optimistic. The Jacobian error bound ϵ_J depends, as we will see, on the method for
 133 approximating $\mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x}_c)$.

134 We will give a result from [19, 21, 31] about the progress of the iteration in the presence of these
 135 errors. The case of interest in this paper is simple and we will give the proof.

136 **THEOREM 2.4.** *Let Assumption 2.1 hold. Let (2.7) and (2.15) hold. Then $\mathbf{J}_c = \mathbf{J}(\mathbf{x}_c)$ is nonsingular*
 137 *and \mathbf{x}_+ , as defined by (2.14), satisfies*

$$138 \quad (2.16) \quad \|\mathbf{e}_+\| = O\left(\|\mathbf{e}_c\|^2 + \epsilon_J\|\mathbf{e}_c\| + \epsilon_F\right).$$

139 *Proof.* We express \mathbf{e}_+ as the sum of the error from Newton's method

$$140 \quad \mathbf{e}_+^N = \mathbf{e}_c - \mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x}_c)^{-1}\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}_c) = O(\|\mathbf{e}_c\|^2)$$

141 and the correction

$$142 \quad (\mathbf{J}_c^{-1} - \mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x}_c)^{-1})\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}_c) - \mathbf{J}_c^{-1}\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{x}_c).$$

143 Equation (2.15) and (2.9) imply that

$$144 \quad \|\mathbf{J}_c - \mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x}_c)\| \leq \frac{1}{2\|\mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x}_c)^{-1}\|},$$

145 and hence we may apply Lemma 2.1 with $\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x}_c)$ and $\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{J}_c$. We may then conclude that

$$146 \quad \|\mathbf{J}_c^{-1}\| \leq 2\|\mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x}_c)^{-1}\| \leq 4\|\mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x}^*)^{-1}\|$$

147 and

$$148 \quad \|\mathbf{J}_c^{-1} - \mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x}_c)^{-1}\| \leq 2\|\mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x}_c)^{-1}\|^2\epsilon_J \leq 8\|\mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x}^*)^{-1}\|^2\epsilon_J = O(\epsilon_J).$$

149 Note that the prefactor in this O -term contains $\|\mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x}^*)^{-1}\|^2$, which, while not so important in this paper,
 150 tells us something about the effects of ill-conditioning on one's freedom to approximate the Jacobian.

151 We now apply (2.12), (2.7), and Lipschitz continuity to obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \|\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}_c)\| &\leq \|\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}^*)\mathbf{e}_c\| + \int_0^1 \|\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}^* + t\mathbf{e}_c) - \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}^*)\| dt \|\mathbf{e}_c\| \\ &\leq (\|\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}^*)\| + \gamma\|\mathbf{e}_c\|)\|\mathbf{e}_c\| = O(\|\mathbf{e}_c\| + \|\mathbf{e}_c\|^2). \end{aligned}$$

152
 153 Combining the terms and using (watch the $\|\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}^*)^{-1}\|$ in the prefactor)

$$\|\mathbf{J}_c^{-1}\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{x}_c)\| \leq \|\mathbf{J}_c^{-1}\|\epsilon_F \leq 4\|\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}^*)^{-1}\|\epsilon_F = O(\epsilon_F)$$

154
 155 completes the proof. □

156 The corollary describing the entire iteration is not a convergence result because the error does not
 157 converge to zero, rather the iteration *stagnates* when $\|\mathbf{e}_n\| = O(\epsilon_F)$. Results of this type are called *local*
 158 *improvement* results in [9].

159 **COROLLARY 2.5.** *Let the assumptions of Corollary 2.3 hold. Assume that (2.15) holds and that ϵ_J is*
 160 *sufficiently small. Then, for all n ,*

$$(2.17) \quad \|\mathbf{e}_{n+1}\| = O(\|\mathbf{e}_n\|^2 + \epsilon_J\|\mathbf{e}_n\| + \epsilon_F),$$

162 where the prefactor in the O -term is independent of n .

163 If, for example, $\epsilon_F = 0$ (exact arithmetic) and ϵ_J is sufficiently small, then the convergence of the
 164 iteration will be q -linear with q -factor $\leq \epsilon_J$. This means that either $\|\mathbf{e}_n\| = 0$ for some $n < \infty$ or

$$\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\|\mathbf{e}_{n+1}\|}{\|\mathbf{e}_n\|} \leq \epsilon_J.$$

165 In a semilog plot of the relative residual history, a linear curve is a sign of q -linear convergence.

166 One case of interest in this paper is when $\epsilon_J = O(\sqrt{\epsilon_F})$. In that case

$$\epsilon_J\|\mathbf{e}_n\| = O(\sqrt{\epsilon_F}\|\mathbf{e}_n\|)$$

167 and hence

$$\|\mathbf{e}_{n+1}\| = O(\|\mathbf{e}_n\|^2 + \epsilon_F).$$

171 Therefore the error in the Jacobian approximation can be neglected in the sense that the estimate for $\|\mathbf{e}_{n+1}\|$
 172 in (2.17) is $O(\|\mathbf{e}_n\|^2 + \epsilon_F)$ with the Jacobian error playing no important role at all. We will clearly see this
 173 in the computations in § 3.

174 In this paper we consider a forward-difference approximation to \mathbf{F}' as the alternative to an analytic
 175 expression. It's useful to look at the scalar case. Let the computed $f(x)$ be

$$\hat{f}(x) = f(x) + e(x) \text{ where } |e(x)| \leq \epsilon_F.$$

176 Then

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\hat{f}(x+h) - \hat{f}(x)}{h} &= \frac{f(x+h) - f(x)}{h} + O(\epsilon_F/h) \\ &= f'(x) + O(h + \epsilon_F/h). \end{aligned}$$

177 If, as is usually the case, the prefactors in the O -terms are benign, then the error is minimized when

$$h = O(\sqrt{\epsilon_F}),$$

178 in which case

$$(2.18) \quad \frac{\hat{f}(x+h) - \hat{f}(x)}{h} = f'(x) + O(\sqrt{\epsilon_F}).$$

183 We warn the reader that the prefactor in the $O(h)$ term for the finite difference approximation is not
 184 guaranteed to be harmless [26]. We also warn the reader of a few assumptions hidden in the derivation of
 185 (2.18). We assume in the derivation that $|x|$ is $O(1)$, *i. e.* not too large nor too small, and that $|f'(x)|$ is not
 186 too small. If $|x|$ is not $O(1)$ then h will need to be scaled to conform to x [19], a detail we can ignore in this
 187 paper because the scaling of the solution in our example problem is $O(1)$. If $|f'(x)|$ is small, then the error
 188 term in (2.18) could be as large as the main term. That is trouble, as we will see in § 3.

189 The forward difference approximation to the Jacobian approximates $\mathbf{F}'(x)$ by $\mathbf{J}(x)$ where the k th column
 190 of \mathbf{J} is

$$191 \quad (2.19) \quad \mathbf{J}_k = \frac{\hat{\mathbf{F}}(\mathbf{x} + h\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_k) - \hat{\mathbf{F}}(\mathbf{x})}{h}$$

192 where $\hat{\mathbf{F}}(x) = \mathbf{F}(x) + \mathbf{E}(x)$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_k$ is the unit vector in the k th coordinate direction. If $h = O(\sqrt{\epsilon_F})$ then
 193 the error in the Jacobian is

$$194 \quad \epsilon_J = O(\sqrt{\epsilon_F}).$$

195 Hence, Theorem 2.4 predicts that there will be no significant difference in the convergence of the nonlinear
 196 iteration between a double precision analytic Jacobian with the linear solve done in double and a forward
 197 difference approximate Jacobian with the linear solve done in single precision. We will see this in the
 198 examples in § 3.2.

199 As an example, consider solving the linear equation for the Newton step with Gaussian elimination.
 200 Think of computing the Jacobian (either analytically or with finite differences) in double precision and then
 201 storing and factoring it in either single or double precision. The discussion above indicates that there will
 202 be no loss in the nonlinear convergence rate if one uses single precision instead of double. There are two
 203 benefits. There is a clear reduction by half in storage if you use single precision. As for cost, there are two
 204 extreme cases of interest.

- 205 • If the cost of evaluating \mathbf{F} and \mathbf{F}' (either analytically or via finite differences) is $o(N^3)$, then the
 206 matrix factorization will be the dominant cost of the computation. Solving the equation for the
 207 Newton step in single precision instead of double will then cut the cost of the nonlinear solve almost
 208 in half. The example in § 3 is like this.
- 209 • Suppose the evaluation of \mathbf{F} is $O(N^2)$ work and a finite difference Jacobian computation is the
 210 only option. Then the cost of evaluating \mathbf{F}' is $O(N^3)$ because each column of the finite difference
 211 Jacobian uses a call to \mathbf{F} . In this case the benefit of a single precision linear solve is less significant.
 212 If the evaluation of \mathbf{F}' is more than $O(N^3)$, then there is little value in a reduced precision linear
 213 solve in terms of cost.

214 **2.2. Backward Error Estimates for LU Factorization.** The local improvement estimate (2.17)
 215 does not take the backward error in the linear solver into account. In fact, most of the literature in nonlinear
 216 equations (for example [6, 8, 19, 20, 27, 29]) makes the implicit assumption that the backward error in the
 217 solver can be neglected and focuses instead on either the forward error in the Jacobian itself $\|\mathbf{J}_c - \mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x}_c)\|$
 218 or a formulation in terms of the inexact Newton condition,

$$219 \quad \|\mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x}_c)\mathbf{s} + \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}_c)\| \leq \eta\|\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}_c)\|,$$

220 which is a small residual condition on the linear equation for the Newton step (2.3).

221 While either of these expressions of error could include the backward error as part of the estimate, that
 222 is not done explicitly and is not part of the discussion or the examples in those papers. One purpose of this
 223 paper is to question the assumption that the backward error can be neglected.

224 The missing component in (2.17) is the backward error in the solver. We let $\hat{\mathbf{L}}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{U}}$ be the computed
 225 LU factors of \mathbf{J} and $\hat{\mathbf{J}} = \hat{\mathbf{L}}\hat{\mathbf{U}}$. The backward error in the solver is

$$226 \quad \delta\mathbf{J} = \hat{\mathbf{J}} - \mathbf{J}.$$

227 The reader should think of \mathbf{J} as an analytic Jacobian or a forward-difference approximation. We will assume,
 228 as is the case in the example in § 3, that $\|\mathbf{J}\|$ is uniformly bounded in the dimension N of the problem.

229 We can incorporate the backward error into (2.17) and obtain,

$$230 \quad \|\mathbf{e}_{n+1}\| = O(\|\mathbf{e}_n\|^2 + (\epsilon_J + \|\delta\mathbf{J}\|)\|\mathbf{e}_n\| + \epsilon_F).$$

231 Since $\epsilon_J = O(\sqrt{\epsilon_F})$ in this paper, we can neglect ϵ_J and have

$$232 \quad (2.20) \quad \|\mathbf{e}_{n+1}\| = O(\|\mathbf{e}_n\|^2 + \|\delta\mathbf{J}\|\|\mathbf{e}_n\| + \epsilon_F),$$

233 clearly exposing the role, if any, of the backward error. The estimate (2.20) suggests that one could attempt
 234 to detect a large backward error via examination of the convergence of the nonlinear iteration, which we do
 235 in § 3.

236 Now let ϵ_p be the precision of the linear solver. This means that we store the Jacobian and do the
 237 factorization and triangular solves with precision ϵ_p . The classic estimate [7, 11] uses the L^1 norm and
 238 contains the dimension N in a nontrivial manner. The first step is an estimate for the component-wise
 239 backward error

$$240 \quad (2.21) \quad |\delta\mathbf{J}|_{ik} \leq \gamma_N(|\hat{\mathbf{L}}|\hat{\mathbf{U}})_{ik},$$

241 where, for a matrix \mathbf{A} , $|\mathbf{A}|$ is the matrix with entries $|\mathbf{A}_{ij}|$, and

$$242 \quad (2.22) \quad \gamma_N = \frac{N\epsilon_p}{1 - N\epsilon_p}.$$

243 The starting point for this estimate of the component-wise backward error is estimation of products of
 244 the form

$$245 \quad \prod_{i=1}^N (1 + \delta_i)^{\rho_i}$$

246 where $|\delta_i| \leq \epsilon_p$ and $\rho_i = \pm 1$. The standard estimate is ([11], page 63)

$$247 \quad (2.23) \quad \left| \prod_{i=1}^N (1 + \delta_i)^{\rho_i} \right| \leq 1 + \gamma_N.$$

248 The final step in the proof of (2.21) is to count the floating point operations in the factorization and use
 249 (2.23).

250 The classic worst case bound for $\|\delta\mathbf{J}\|$ uses the L^1 matrix norm, *i. e.* the maximum column sum. We will
 251 use the L^1 norm in this part of the paper for that reason. However, the rest of the paper is norm-independent
 252 and uses the L^1 estimates as guidance, a reasonable idea since only the magnitude of the bound is important
 253 in most applications [11]. With (2.22), the norm estimate is

$$254 \quad \|\delta\mathbf{J}\|_1 \leq \gamma_N \|\hat{\mathbf{L}}\|_1 \|\hat{\mathbf{U}}\|_1.$$

255 The magnitudes of the entries of $\hat{\mathbf{L}}$ are bounded by 1. The worst case would be if $|\hat{\mathbf{L}}_{i1}| = 1$ for all i .
 256 Then

$$257 \quad \|\hat{\mathbf{L}}\|_1 = N.$$

258 Following [7], we define the growth factor

$$259 \quad g = \max_{1 \leq i, j \leq N} \frac{\max |\hat{\mathbf{U}}_{ij}|}{|\mathbf{J}_{ij}|}.$$

260 Hence, again using the worst case estimate for the L^1 norm of \mathbf{U}

$$261 \quad \|\hat{\mathbf{U}}\|_1 \leq gN \|\mathbf{J}\|_1.$$

262 So, at this point we have

$$263 \quad \|\delta\mathbf{J}\|_1 \leq \gamma_N N^2 g \epsilon_p = O(\epsilon_p g N^3).$$

264 While the growth factor g can be as large as 2^{N-1} , that is a worst-case bound first seen in a famous
 265 example and only rarely seen in practice ([11], page 177–178). However, one can justify neglecting g in most
 266 applications, so we will do that.

267 Since $\|\mathbf{J}\|_1 = O(1)$, we obtain, neglecting g ,

$$268 \quad (2.24) \quad \|\delta\mathbf{J}\|_1 \leq \gamma_N N^2 \epsilon_p = O(N^3 \epsilon_p).$$

269 This is, as the textbooks clearly say, ridiculous. For example, if $\epsilon_J \approx 10^{-16}$, then the backward error is
 270 $O(1)$ for any $N > 250,000$ and $> .001$ for $N > 21,000$. This would tell us that we should expect Gaussian
 271 elimination with column pivoting to return only three figures of accuracy for some fairly small problems and
 272 says that $\|\delta\mathbf{J}\|$ could cause some real trouble with slow convergence of Newton’s method. This pessimism is
 273 not confirmed by practice.

274 We can obtain a more realistic bound than (2.24) if we replace the worst case bound for $\|\hat{\mathbf{L}}\|_1$ and $\|\hat{\mathbf{U}}\|_1$
 275 with the best-case, $\|\hat{\mathbf{L}}\|_1 = O(1)$ and $\|\hat{\mathbf{U}}\|_1 = O(\|\mathbf{J}\|_1) = O(1)$. Then we have

$$276 \quad (2.25) \quad \|\delta\mathbf{J}\|_1 \leq \gamma_N \epsilon_p = O(\epsilon_p N).$$

277 This is much better. Remember we want $\|\delta\mathbf{J}\|_1 = O(\sqrt{\epsilon_F})$. If ϵ_F is double precision unit roundoff ($1.1 \times$
 278 10^{-16}), $\epsilon_J = O(\sqrt{\epsilon_F})$ (think of a forward difference approximation), and $\epsilon_p = \epsilon_F$ (i.e. we do the solve in
 279 double precision), then (2.25) tells us that $\|\delta\mathbf{J}\| = O(\sqrt{\epsilon_F})$ as long as $N < 10^8$. Problems with dimension
 280 $N > 10^8$ are far too large for dense matrix Gaussian elimination on a typical desktop computer, so we can
 281 expect the backward error to have little effect on the nonlinear iteration.

282 We will consider doing the linear solver in a lower precision after making our estimate of $\|\delta\mathbf{J}\|$ even
 283 more optimistic. New results in probabilistic roundoff analysis [13, 14] attempt to make theory better reflect
 284 practice.

285 The new formulation of (2.23) in [13] is a probabilistic statement. The advantage is that one can replace
 286 γ_N with

$$287 \quad \tilde{\gamma}_N(\lambda) = \exp\left(\lambda\sqrt{N}\epsilon_p + \frac{N\epsilon_p^2}{1-\epsilon_p}\right) - 1 = \lambda\sqrt{N}\epsilon_p + O(\epsilon_p^2),$$

288 where λ can be tuned as we will see below. The analog to (2.23) (Theorem 2.4, page A2819 in [13]) is

289 **THEOREM 2.6.** *Let $\{\delta_j\}_{j=1}^N$ be independent random variables with mean zero and bounded in absolute*
 290 *value by ϵ_p . Then, for any $\lambda > 0$ the bound*

$$291 \quad (2.26) \quad \left| \prod_{i=1}^N (1 + \delta_i)^{\rho_i} \right| \leq 1 + \tilde{\gamma}_N(\lambda)$$

292 *holds with probability at least*

$$293 \quad P(\lambda) = 1 - 2\exp\left(\frac{-\lambda^2(1-\epsilon_p)^2}{2}\right).$$

294 Since λ is a free parameter and $P(\lambda) \rightarrow 1$ very rapidly as $\lambda \rightarrow \infty$, one can increase λ to make $P(\lambda)$ near
 295 one and still obtain a bound of $O(\sqrt{N}\epsilon_p)$ with high probability for the left side of (2.26). We will give a
 296 concrete example when we state the result from [13] for the backward error in the LU factorization.

297 The application to the backward error for LU is not as straightforward as in the deterministic case.
 298 While counting operations is still the way to obtain the bound, the probability term is more complicated.
 299 Define

$$300 \quad Q(\lambda, N) = 1 - N(1 - P(\lambda)).$$

301 **Theorem 2.7** (Theorem 3.6, page A2824 in [13]) is the component-wise backward error estimate.

302 **THEOREM 2.7.** *Assume that all errors in every binary operation in Gaussian elimination are independent*
 303 *random variables of mean zero. Let $\lambda > 0$ be given. Then the computed LU factors from Gaussian elimination*
 304 *on $\mathbf{J} \in R^{N \times N}$ satisfy*

$$305 \quad \hat{\mathbf{L}}\hat{\mathbf{U}} = \hat{\mathbf{J}} = \mathbf{J} + \delta\mathbf{J},$$

306 where

$$307 \quad (2.27) \quad |\delta\mathbf{J}| \leq \tilde{\gamma}_N(\lambda) |\hat{\mathbf{L}}| |\hat{\mathbf{U}}| = (\lambda\sqrt{N}\epsilon_p + O(\epsilon_p^2)) |\hat{\mathbf{L}}| |\hat{\mathbf{U}}|$$

308 holds with probability at least $Q(\lambda, N^3/3 + N^2/2 + N/6)$.

309 Now one is free to adjust λ . Using $\lambda = \sqrt{\log(N)}$ for the largest N of interest is one approach. An
 310 example from [13, 14] illustrates the result. If we set $\lambda = 13$, then the probability that (2.27) fails to hold is

$$311 \quad (N^3/3 + N^2/2 + 7N/6)P(13) \approx 1.3 * 10^{-7} \text{ for } N \leq 10^{10} .$$

312 In this case (2.25) can be improved to

$$313 \quad (2.28) \quad |\delta\mathbf{J}| \leq (13\sqrt{N}\epsilon_p + O(\epsilon_p^2)) |\hat{\mathbf{L}}| |\hat{\mathbf{U}}|,$$

314 for $N \leq 10^{10}$, and hence for all desktop-sized problems.

315 Returning to general norms and the case $\|\mathbf{F}'\| = O(1)$, the idea for this paper is that (2.28) implies that,
 316 with high probability, we can use (neglecting the ϵ_p^2 terms)

$$317 \quad (2.29) \quad \|\delta\mathbf{J}\| \leq 13\sqrt{N}\epsilon_p$$

318 for the values of N of interest under our best-case assumptions that $\|\hat{\mathbf{U}}\|$ and $\|\hat{\mathbf{L}}\|$ are $O(1)$. We will explore
 319 some consequences of that below and report on numerical observations in § 3.

320 Now consider the case where $\epsilon_p = \epsilon_s = 6.0 \times 10^{-8} = O(\sqrt{\epsilon_F})$ is single precision unit roundoff. In that
 321 case (2.28) tells us that we cannot completely neglect the backward error unless N is very small, say < 10
 322 However, (2.20) implies that the $\|\delta\mathbf{J}\|$ term on the right side of (2.20) will only become important when
 323 $\|\mathbf{e}_n\| \approx \|\delta\mathbf{J}\|$ and this will only happen at the end of the iteration. For example, if $N = 10000$ and we neglect
 324 the norms of the LU factors, then, with high probability, $\|\delta\mathbf{J}\| \leq 7.8 \times 10^{-5}$. In that case (2.25) and (2.20)
 325 indicate that the convergence will be q-linear, but still fast enough to be useful. The estimate also shows
 326 that that $\|\delta\mathbf{J}\| \|\mathbf{e}_n\|$ will be the dominant term in (2.20) only if $\|\mathbf{e}_n\| \leq 8 \times 10^{-5}$, *i. e.* for the last one or two
 327 iterations before stagnation. Figure 3.4 illustrates this, but the effect is visible only very near stagnation.

328 Many computing environments support half precision computations. Unlike double and single precision,
 329 which conform to the IEEE standard [16, 30], there are many half precision formats. This paper will focus
 330 on IEEE half precision (see Table 3.5, page 23 in [16]). If we do the linear solves in half precision, then
 331 $\epsilon_p = \epsilon_h = 4.9 \times 10^{-4}$. We can invoke (2.28) and (2.20) to predict that the nonlinear iteration will see the
 332 effects of large N much earlier than a single precision computation, so we can expect to see the reduction
 333 in convergence rate more readily. If, for example, $N = 10000$, we should expect to converge slowly, if at all,
 334 because the estimate is that $|\delta\mathbf{J}| \leq .64$ The largest half precision computation we could do for this paper
 335 had size $N = 16,384$, for which the estimate for $|\delta\mathbf{J}| \approx .8$. So as the dimension increases, the deterioration
 336 in the convergence rate should be clearly visible. This is something we can test on a desktop computer. The
 337 results in § 3 show that this estimate is still pessimistic.

338 We will explore these estimates in § 3 by solving a nonlinear problem and increasing the dimension to
 339 see if one can observe changes in the nonlinear convergence rates. (2.29) suggests that we will see very little
 340 differences between single precision and double precision and a significant difference between half precision
 341 and either single or double precision.

342 **3. Example: Chandrasekhar H-Equation.** As an example we consider the mid-point rule dis-
 343 cretization of the Chandrasekhar H-equation [3],

$$344 \quad (3.1) \quad \mathcal{F}(H)(\mu) = H(\mu) - \left(1 - \frac{c}{2} \int_0^1 \frac{\mu H(\mu)}{\mu + \nu} d\nu \right)^{-1} = 0.$$

345 The nonlinear operator \mathcal{F} is defined on $C[0, 1]$, the space of continuous functions on $[0, 1]$.

346 This equation has a well-understood dependence on the parameter c [4, 28]. The equation has unique
 347 solutions at $c = 0$ and $c = 1$ and two solutions for $0 < c < 1$. There is a simple fold singularity [18] at
 348 $c = 1$. Only one [2, 3] of the two solutions for $0 < c < 1$ is of physical interest and that is the one easiest to

349 find numerically. One must perform a continuation computation to find the other one. The structure of the
 350 singularity is preserved if one discretizes the integral with any quadrature rule with positive weights that
 351 integrates constants exactly.

352 For the purposes of this paper the composite midpoint rule will suffice. The N -point composite midpoint
 353 rule is

$$354 \quad \int_0^1 f(\nu) d\nu \approx \frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=1}^N f(\nu_j)$$

355 where $\nu_j = (j - 1/2)/N$ for $1 \leq j \leq N$. This rule is second-order accurate for sufficiently smooth functions
 356 f . The solution of (3.1) is, however, not smooth enough. $H'(\mu)$ has a logarithmic singularity at $\mu = 0$. We
 357 will use the L^2 norm to compute $\|\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x})\|$ in the tables and figures.

358 Increasing N has no effect on the conditioning of the Jacobian nor, if the backward error in the linear
 359 solve can truly be neglected, on the iteration statistics [1, 25]. Hence we can clearly, but indirectly, observe
 360 the effects of N on the Jacobian backward error through the performance of the nonlinear solver.

361 The discrete problem is

$$362 \quad (3.2) \quad \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x})_i \equiv x_i - \left(1 - \frac{c}{2N} \sum_{j=1}^N \frac{x_j \mu_i}{\mu_j + \mu_i} \right)^{-1} = 0.$$

363 One can simplify the approximate integral operator in (3.2) and expose some useful structure. Since

$$364 \quad \frac{c}{2N} \sum_{j=1}^N \frac{x_j \mu_i}{\mu_j + \mu_i} = \frac{c(i - 1/2)}{2N} \sum_{j=1}^N \frac{x_j}{i + j - 1},$$

365 the approximate integral operator is the product of a diagonal matrix and a Hankel matrix and one can use
 366 a fast Fourier transform to evaluate the operator-vector product with $O(N \log(N))$ work [10, 21].

367 We can express the approximation of the integral operator in matrix form

$$368 \quad \mathbf{M}(\mathbf{x})_{ij} = \frac{c(i - 1/2)}{2N} \sum_{j=1}^N \frac{x_j}{i + j - 1}$$

369 and compute the Jacobian analytically as

$$370 \quad \mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{I} - \text{diag}(\mathbf{G}(\mathbf{x}))^2 \mathbf{M}(\mathbf{x}),$$

371 where

$$372 \quad \mathbf{G}(\mathbf{x})_i = \left(1 - \frac{c}{2N} \sum_{j=1}^N \frac{x_j \mu_i}{\mu_j + \mu_i} \right)^{-1}.$$

373 Hence the data for the Jacobian is already available after one computes $\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{x} - \mathbf{G}(\mathbf{x})$ and the Jacobian
 374 can be computed with $O(N^2)$ work. We do that in this example and therefore the only part of the solve
 375 that requires $O(N^3)$ work is the matrix factorization.

376 One could also approximate the Jacobian with forward differences using (2.19) at a cost of N function
 377 evaluations. As we saw in § 2, if one computes \mathbf{F} in double precision with unit roundoff ϵ_F , then $h = O(\sqrt{\epsilon_F})$
 378 is a reasonable choice [19]. In that case the error in the Jacobian is $O(\sqrt{\epsilon_F}) = O(\epsilon_s)$ where ϵ_s is unit roundoff
 379 in single precision. The cost of a finite difference Jacobian in this example is $O(N^2 \log(N))$ work.

380 The analysis in § 2 suggests that there is no significant difference in the nonlinear iteration from either
 381 the choice of analytic or finite difference Jacobians or the choice of single or double precision for the linear
 382 solver. The results in § 3.2 support that suggestion.

383 One should be more cautious with half precision because the error in the solver is larger than single
 384 precision roundoff, so we would expect linear convergence prior to stagnation at best. In § 3.3 we see linear

385 convergence and show that the convergence rate of the nonlinear solver does degrade with dimension for
386 small problems sizes, but eventually stabilizes.

387 In all cases the initial iterate \mathbf{x}_0 had all components equal to one. We consider three cases. If $c = .5$ or
388 $c = .99$ the Jacobian is nonsingular and the theory in § 2 is applicable. The case $c = 1.0$ is different because
389 the Jacobian is singular at the solution.

390 **3.1. Computations.** The computations reported in this section were done in Julia v 1.5.3 on a 2019
391 Apple iMac with eight cores and 64GB of memory. Julia supports half precision in software and so com-
392 putations in half precision are very slow. We report on computations for dimensions $N = 2^{10} \dots 2^{14}$. The
393 results for half precision required two weeks of computer time and increasing the dimension beyond 2^{14} was
394 not practical. In all the figures we plot the relative residual $\|\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}_n)\|/\|\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}_0)\|$ as a function of the iteration
395 counter n . This is a reasonable surrogate for the errors in the nonsingular cases $c = .5$ and $c = .99$ in view
396 of (2.13). In the singular case $c = 1$, $\|\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}_n)\|/\|\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}_0)\| = O(\|\mathbf{e}_n\|^2)$ [4]. However, even in that case we can
397 observe the effects, if any, of backward error in the Jacobian using the relative residual.

398 In the computations we computed the analytic Jacobian in double precision and then stored and factored
399 the Jacobian in double, single, or half precision (the solver precision). We computed the columns of the
400 forward difference Jacobian in double precision using (2.19) and then stored them in the solver precision to
401 build the forward difference Jacobian. The factorization and triangular solves were carried out in the solver
402 precision. We converted the residual to the solver precision before computing the step. This conversion keeps
403 the solver from promoting the intermediate steps in the solve in Julia and is important for performance. By
404 the way, Matlab does this conversion automatically. In half precision one must also scale the residual before
405 the conversion to avoid underflow errors [15]. After the solve the step was automatically promoted to double
406 precision upon addition to the current nonlinear iteration.

407 The computations used the author’s SIAMFANLEquation.jl Julia package [22–24]. The files (codes,
408 data, and an IJulia notebook) for these results are available at

409 <https://github.com/ctkelley/MPResults>.

410 The solvers with the SIAMFANLEquation.jl package are available at

411 <https://github.com/ctkelley/SIAMFANLEquations.jl>.

412 **3.2. Can You Tell the Difference Between Single and Double?** We consider two cases $c = .5$
413 and $c = .99$ with nonsingular Jacobian. Theorem 2.4 is applicable. We see a difference in the convergence
414 because the Jacobian for $c = .99$ is nearer to singularity than for $c = .5$. In these cases Figures 3.2 and
415 3.1 show very little dependence of the iteration histories on either the precision of the factorization or the
416 use of a finite difference or analytic Jacobian. The only meaningful difference is the third iteration for $c = .5$,
417 The iteration is very near stagnation in that case and the analytic Jacobian combined with a factorization in
418 double precision reaches stagnation before the other three methods, all of which have a Jacobian with error
419 $O(\sqrt{\epsilon_F})$. In all cases, if one were to terminate the iteration when the relative residual fell below 10^{-8} , then
420 all the iterations in Figures 3.1 and 3.2 would stop at the same iteration (3 for $c = .5$ and 5 for $c = .99$).

421 The singular case $c = 1$ is very different [4]. The assumptions of Theorem 2.4 do not hold and we do not
422 see the behavior that the theorem predicts. To begin with, the convergence is not quadratic, but q-linear
423 with q-factor $1/2$. Moreover, the initial iterate must not only be near the solution, but the initial error must
424 be mostly in the direction of the null space of the Jacobian at the solution. We see q-linear convergence in
425 Figure 3.3. One way to understand the convergence rate is to solve $x^2 = 0$ with Newton’s method. The
426 iteration is

427
$$x_{n+1} = x_n - \frac{x_n^2}{2x_n} = x_n/2$$

428 giving a q-factor of $1/2$. The structure of the singularity of the H-equation is very similar to this in the
429 component of the error in the direction of the null space of the Jacobian at the solution.

430 One can also see that convergence history is very different for the forward difference approximation to
431 the Jacobian. In the scalar case, for example, if $f'(x) = 0$, then the relative error in the finite difference
432 approximation can be large and the estimate (2.18) is true, but not very useful. This is especially the case if
433 ϵ_F is an absolute error, which is often the case. As an example, let $f(x) = \cos(x)$, $x = 10^{-6}$, and $h = 10^{-7}$.
434 The $f'(x) = -\sin(x) \approx -x$. The finite difference approximation is $\approx -1.05 \times 10^{-6}$ and has only two figures
435 of accuracy.

FIG. 3.1. Residual Histories: Single and Double Precision, $c = .5$

436 As in the scalar case, if $\mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x})$ is singular or nearly so then the finite-difference approximation may be
 437 poor in directions in the null space of $\mathbf{F}'(\mathbf{x})$. Moreover, the estimate (2.17) for the nonlinear iteration depends
 438 on nonsingularity of the Jacobian. We should not be surprised when things go wrong and see an example of
 439 this in Figure 3.3.

FIG. 3.2. Residual Histories: Single and Double Precision, $c = .99$

FIG. 3.3. Residual Histories: Single and Double Precision, $c = 1.0$

440 **3.3. Half Precision: How low can you go?** We begin with the case of nonsingular Jacobian: $c = .5$
 441 and $c = .99$. As you can see from the figures, the convergence is not quadratic, but q-linear. This is because
 442 of the large Jacobian error. Also the results with a finite difference Jacobian were essentially the same, with
 443 no visible difference in the plots. The convergence rates agreed to three figures and we only present the rate
 444 estimates for the analytic Jacobian in the tables.

445 In the half precision computations we can see the difference in convergence speed between the $c = .5$
 446 case and the case nearer to singularity $c = .99$. There was little difference between the analytic Jacobian and
 447 the forward difference approximation for these two cases. However, the nonlinear iteration statistics were
 448 very different and the change in convergence rate as a function of dimension for $c = .99$ is easy to see.

449 In Figures 3.4 and 3.5 we show the dependence of the nonlinear convergence rate on dimension when the
 450 matrix factorization is done in half precision. The remarkable thing about the plots is that the convergence
 451 rates do not seem to depend on dimension in the easy ($c = .5$) case and stop becoming slower as the dimension
 452 increases beyond $N = 4096$ for the nearly singular case ($c = .99$). Tables 3.1 and 3.2 show numerically that
 453 the convergence rates $\|\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}_{n+1})\|/\|\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}_n)\|$ are essentially independent of dimension for the $c = .5$ case and
 454 stabilize after $N = 4096$ for the $c = .99$ case. This explains the overlap in the plots after $N = 4096$. Both
 455 the plots and the tables indicate that the solver error is not increasing with dimension.

FIG. 3.4. Residual Histories: Half Precision, $c = .5$

456 The singular case, $c = 1$, is particularly interesting in half precision for two reasons. The first is that the
 457 convergence rate seems, both from Figure 3.6 and Table 3.3 to be worse than q-linear. This is, in fact, what
 458 happens with singular problems of this type when the Jacobian approximation is poor [5]. The equation
 459 $f(x) = x^2 = 0$ is a good example. If $x_0 = 1$ and we approximate $f'(x)$ by $f'(x_0) = 2$, then it is easy to show

TABLE 3.1
Half Precision Computed Convergence Rates: $\|\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}_{n+1})\|/\|\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}_n)\|$, $c = .5$

n	1024	2048	4096	8192	16384
1	1.56706e-01	1.56708e-01	1.56708e-01	1.56705e-01	1.56706e-01
2	1.53569e-01	1.53573e-01	1.53579e-01	1.53578e-01	1.53576e-01
3	1.52949e-01	1.52944e-01	1.52946e-01	1.52948e-01	1.52949e-01
4	1.52853e-01	1.52848e-01	1.52844e-01	1.52847e-01	1.52843e-01
5	1.52831e-01	1.52829e-01	1.52832e-01	1.52830e-01	1.52830e-01
6	1.52828e-01	1.52825e-01	1.52826e-01	1.52830e-01	1.52827e-01
7	1.52830e-01	1.52824e-01	1.52827e-01	1.52826e-01	1.52825e-01
8	1.52832e-01	1.52832e-01	1.52824e-01	1.52825e-01	1.52828e-01
9	1.52838e-01	1.52830e-01	1.52831e-01	1.52830e-01	1.52826e-01
10	1.52828e-01	1.52828e-01	1.52827e-01	1.52829e-01	1.52827e-01

FIG. 3.5. *Residual Histories: Half Precision, $c = .99$*

460 that

461

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{x_n}{2/n} = 1.$$

462 This is very poor sublinear convergence.

463

464

Secondly, after 30 iterations the error is still too large for the effects of the forward difference approximate Jacobian to be seen. So both sides of Figure 3.6 are identical and the convergence statistics cease to depend

FIG. 3.6. Residual Histories: Half Precision, $c = 1$

TABLE 3.2
Half Precision Computed Convergence Rates: $\|\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}_{n+1})\|/\|\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}_n)\|$, $c = .99$

n	1024	2048	4096	8192	16384
1	2.63294e-01	4.88603e-01	5.06480e-01	5.06480e-01	5.06480e-01
2	1.39099e-01	4.50348e-01	5.83959e-01	5.83962e-01	5.83961e-01
3	1.44278e-01	4.13186e-01	6.38900e-01	6.38900e-01	6.38898e-01
4	1.01754e-01	3.60960e-01	6.64343e-01	6.77977e-01	6.77976e-01
5	9.42216e-02	3.76718e-01	6.78547e-01	7.06190e-01	7.06192e-01
6	1.03855e-01	3.36916e-01	7.12325e-01	7.26959e-01	7.26957e-01
7	8.71357e-02	4.10487e-01	6.98753e-01	7.42506e-01	7.42507e-01
8	9.85171e-02	3.63814e-01	7.53512e-01	7.54294e-01	7.54296e-01
9	9.81771e-02	3.73218e-01	7.13812e-01	7.63337e-01	7.63337e-01
10	7.82248e-02	3.60341e-01	7.51307e-01	7.70318e-01	7.70319e-01

TABLE 3.3
Half Precision Computed Convergence Rates: $\|\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}_{n+1})\|/\|\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}_n)\|$, $c = 1$

n	1024	2048	4096	8192	16384
1	2.89271e-01	4.97487e-01	5.18347e-01	5.18347e-01	5.18347e-01
2	2.02306e-01	4.37133e-01	6.02756e-01	6.02754e-01	6.02755e-01
3	3.04726e-01	4.60824e-01	6.62228e-01	6.64944e-01	6.64946e-01
4	3.28286e-01	4.37880e-01	6.87719e-01	7.11345e-01	7.11344e-01
5	4.09534e-01	5.29573e-01	7.12647e-01	7.46800e-01	7.46800e-01
6	4.67802e-01	5.59574e-01	7.46514e-01	7.74644e-01	7.74642e-01
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮
26	9.37645e-01	9.02116e-01	8.63996e-01	9.30262e-01	9.30264e-01
27	8.64444e-01	8.84138e-01	9.57200e-01	9.32602e-01	9.32599e-01
28	9.50195e-01	9.80767e-01	9.72447e-01	9.34786e-01	9.34786e-01
29	8.76453e-01	8.51197e-01	8.62460e-01	9.36834e-01	9.36837e-01
30	9.42673e-01	9.90469e-01	9.56378e-01	9.38760e-01	9.38762e-01

466 **4. Conclusions.** We showed how to indirectly observe the backward error in an LU factorization
467 through the iteration statistics in Newton’s method. For single precision, we confirm both the recent theory
468 and folklore that storing and factoring the Jacobian in single precision has minimal effect on the performance
469 of the nonlinear iteration. The backward error in the linear solver for the half precision case is large enough
470 to degrade the nonlinear convergence to q-linear. Even so, we see that the results for the linear solver depend
471 less on dimension than the theory predicts. Storing and factoring the Jacobian in half precision only seems
472 useful for very well-conditioned problems.

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